

1 **Transcriptional properties of human papillomavirus type 5 and type 8, the epidermodysplasia**
2 **verruciforma (EV) HPVs.**

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7 Human papillomaviruses are stratified into high and low risk based on oncogenic potential. Low risk HPVs
8 of the alpha genus (e.g., HPV11) cause genital warts, while high risk alpha genus HPVs (e.g., HPV16 and
9 HPV18) cause cancer of the cervix, head and neck, and likely other organs. Beta genus papillomaviruses,
10 like HPV5 and HPV8 infect the skin rather than the anogenital mucosa. HPV5 and HPV8 are described to
11 contribute or cause skin cancer but their transcriptional properties and causative role in oncogenes is less
12 well established than for HPV16 and HPV18. We studied total transcription in human cells expressing E5,
13 E6, or E7 of HPV5 and HPV8, as well as in cells expressing the complete early region of HPV8 (containing
14 E2, E3, E4, E5 and E6). We describe transcriptional functions of the E7 oncogene of HPV5 and HPV8
15 that are conserved with that of high risk HPV16 and HPV18. Activation of the retinoblastoma-like pocket
16 protein p107 was a conserved transcriptional function of HPV5 and HPV8 E7 with HPV16 and HPV18 and
17 likely indicated a conserved compensatory response to Rb1 inhibition by E7. Activation of a DNA damage
18 program characterized by induction of BRCA1, CHEK1, BLM helicase, and genes of the XRCC family was
19 a conserved transcriptional property of HPV5 and HPV8 E7 and alluded to genomic instability preceding
20 transformation tumor suppression loss resulting from Rb1 destabilization.
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